
University St. Kliment Ohridski Bitola
Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Ohrid

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector
INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024

CIP - Каталогизација во публикација
Национална и универзитетска библиотека "Св. Климент Охридски",
Скопје

338.48(062)

33(062)

338.47(062)

640.4(062)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference on Service sector INSCOSES (17 ;
2024 ; Ohrid)

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES ; XVII International Scientific
Conference on Service sector INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024
[Електронски извор] / [organizing committee Aleksandar Trajkov ... и
др.]. - Текст во PDF формат, содржи 435 стр., илустр. - Ohrid : Faculty
of tourism and hospitality, 2025

Начин на пристапување (URL): <https://zenodo.org/communities/inscoses/>
(Слободен пристап). - Наслов преземен од екранот. - Опис на изворот на
ден 26.02.2025. - Библиографија кон трудовите

ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

а) Туризам -- Собири б) Гастрономија -- Собири в) Економија -- Собири г)
Царина -- Собири

COBISS.MK-ID 65372677

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector INSCOSES, Ohrid,
26-27 September 2024
ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

UDK 338.48-6:7/8(497.16)
338.483.12:930.85]:303.62(497.16)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14972624

RETRO MARKETING AND TITOGRAD: NON – DARK TOURISM PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

In the post-socialist era, Montenegro has evolved into a growing destination brand but has also become the European country most reliant on tourism. After the COVID-19 pandemic, with a new wave of nationalism, migration, economic crises and fear of terrorism sweeping through Europe, the phenomenon of retro marketing and nostalgia as tourism motive are strengthening.

This paper aims to explore modalities of revitalizing of tangible and intangible cultural heritage connected with the former president of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, Marshal Josip Broz Tito, focusing on Podgorica, formerly known as Titograd. The paper will implement survey methods and *in situ* research to examine themed experiences and attractions for tourists and visitors based on historical time travel to Titograd. Non - dark tourism perceptible in the paper aims to link collective spirit and solidarity as fundamental social values in the SFRY with contemporary concept of sustainable tourism destination.

KEY WORDS: retro marketing, nostalgic tourism, Titograd, tangible and intangible cultural heritage

INTRODUCTION

Following the civilizational shift introduced by the Information Age and the transition to a society and economy where access to knowledge-based information is the key source of development and competitiveness, a new marketing paradigm, the Experience Economy, emerged at the end of the 20th century (*Pine, J; Gilmor, J, 1999*). Although present for over two and a half decades, the Experience Economy has only become a full socio-economic reality in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. Within this concept, experience is regarded as a crucial element of sustainable competitive advantage, especially in service industries such as tourism, trade, etc. Therefore, in the Experience Economy, consumers do not merely purchase a mix of products and services; they acquire experiences that provide memories and sensations (*Vrhovski, 2012*). There are five principles identified in the creation of experiences (*Pine B. J., Gilmore J. H, 1998*): theming the experience, harmonizing impressions with positive cues (consumer perception), eliminating negative cues (removing elements that detract from or oppose the experience theme), creating souvenirs or tangible reminders of the experience, which will stimulate all five senses to fully engage the consumer. These principles are used to create value within destinations or enterprises to enhance the experiences of tourists and visitors.

Destination experience can be gained through various occurrences, either spontaneous or orchestrated. In tourism, an experience occurs when an enterprise or institution involves and engages tourists and visitors (co-creation) and can be stimulated by travel, museum exhibitions, events, food, etc. From this perspective, retro motifs and the evocation of nostalgic feelings have proven to be effective marketing communication tools. While the use of nostalgia in marketing is not new, it is continuously growing and encompasses nostalgia for geographic destinations, past eras, personalities that no longer exist, and more. One example of evoking nostalgic emotions in consumers is found in tourism, specifically in the nostalgic content offered by tourist destinations.

At the beginning of the 21st century, Germany, Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, and other countries began to valorise their former socialist cultural heritage for tourism. Some theorists (*Ivanov, S.H, 2020*) identify “five characteristics of communist heritage tourism: ideologically overburdened type of tourism, controversial, represents a limited time period of history,

represents a personality cult, concentration of resources in places related with communist history in the country (in cities and the countryside).” Socialist contents are valorised both from the perspective of nostalgia and trauma, alongside commodification, i.e., the transformation of cultural heritage into a commodity (Georgiescu, D, 2016). Examples of memorial value valorisation include Checkpoint Charlie and the DDR Museum of Everyday Life in Berlin, the Museum of Communism in Prague, Memento Park with communist sculptures in Budapest, and the House of the People in Bucharest (Light, D, 2000). In Slovenia, for more than 15 years, there have been tourist attractions related to the tangible and intangible cultural heritage of the former SFRY. This is supported by the notion: “It is impossible to ignore a period of history together with its historical effects and, therefore, socialism’s heritage represents great tourism potential” (Balažič, G, 2011). In Brioni, Croatia, where Marshal Tito, the long-standing president of the SFRY, spent a lot of time, tourists can view his photos with renowned film stars and ride in his Cadillac *El Dorado*, followed by a visit to Barren Island (Goli Otok), the site of suffering for many opponents of Tito's political system (Duda, K, 2014). In Serbia, it is now possible to rent Tito’s exclusive “*Blue Train*” for celebrations, business, and corporate events (Velikonja, M. 2008), while in Subotica there is an eco-themed park “Yugoland” that preserves memories of certain aspects of life in the SFRY and initiates efforts to formalize the Yugoslav national minority in the country. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, tourists can visit Tito's nuclear bunker in Konjic, which today serves as a meeting place for artists from the region and beyond.

Following this perspective, a question arises concerning the justification of tourism initiatives in Montenegro for the preservation and revitalization of cultural heritage from the period of Tito's Yugoslavia. This paper will discuss the possibility of valorising the narrative of “Tito” as the personification of antifascism, as well as the socialist cultural heritage of Titograd, outside the context of dark tourism and without attributing Yugonostalgic connotations, guided by the principles of the experience economy.

The first part of this paper is based on desk research and literature review, utilizing methods such as observation, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, description, etc. In addition to the narrative discourse, this paper includes *in situ* research in Podgorica. During June and July 2024, 150 surveys were distributed, and 105 completed surveys were collected in bars and restaurants predominantly frequented by local residents, as well as in scientific and educational institutions, governmental and non-governmental organizations. Since the survey research is focused on the attitudes of the local

population, specifically the local community of Podgorica, it is limited in terms of the participation of tourists themselves. Therefore, their perspectives will be a potential topic for further research.

RETROMARKETING AND THE CONCEPT OF NOSTALGIA IN MARKETING

Retromarketing, or nostalgic marketing, represents a concept that has seen growing popularity in recent years, both in marketing theory and business practice (*Membali-Pollán, M; Ramos López, D; Crespo-Pereira, V, 2022*). In today's highly competitive market, retro trends connect different generations of consumers in marketing communication (*Holtova, M; Kadekova, Z; Košičiarova, I, 2019*). The concept of nostalgia, as a powerful emotion encompassing both joy and sorrow, is increasingly attracting the interest of researchers, particularly concerning consumer behaviour in the service sector (*Weingarten, E. and Wei, Z, 2023*). Some studies show that nostalgia, as a marketing tool, encourages consumers to make purchases by promising a return to happier times (*Holtova, M; Kadekova, Z; Košičiarova, I, 2019*). Consequently, brand managers have used nostalgia in marketing campaigns for years. On the other hand, tourists visit numerous destinations worldwide for their historical significance, which involves integrating historical and retro narratives about events, situations, themes, or personalities into the destination's image (*Schibik, A. J., Shields, P. O., and Schibik, T. J., 2023*).

Image 1: Retro Poster of Kotor Bay¹⁰

¹⁰ Source: <https://fineartamerica.com/featured/1-boka-kotorska-long-shot.html?product=poster>

After the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the waves of conflict and migration in Europe and beyond, there has been a notable increase in the application of retro trends. In the wake of global crises, there is a heightened need among people for security. The expansion of virtual communication during and after the pandemic (*Baltezarević, R, 2021*) has contributed to the frequent application of retromarketing and a focus on past times that appear more carefree in the eyes of consumers.

DESTINATION IMAGE OF MONTENEGRO IN THE SFRY

After World War II, in the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY), notable for its geopolitical position between the “East“ and the “West“, tourism became an important part of the country's identity. Unlike other socialist countries, Yugoslavs were free to travel, and the country positioned itself as a distinctive mass tourism destination. The touristification of the country was, among other things, facilitated through youth labour brigades and youth labour actions. Namely, more than three million Yugoslav young people participated in these brigades and actions, engaging in large-scale voluntary labour aimed at implementing projects for the common good (*Grandits, H. and Taylor, K, 2010*).

Yugoslavia received international recognition due to its fight against fascism, resistance to Stalinism, and its leadership in the Non-Aligned Movement, which united over one billion people, giving the SFRY a position “more significant than ever in the history of the South Slavs“ (*Matvejević, P., 2013*). Due to the long rule of the president Josip Broz Tito, SFRY was often referred to as Tito's Yugoslavia. During the rule of this influential statesman (1945-1980), numerous world-renowned figures in politics and culture experienced Yugoslav tourism, which was seen as a unique socialist experiment in the process of establishing Yugoslav identity (*Antešević, N., 2023*). The emergence of “Yugo-tourism“, primarily perceived as low-budget beach tourism “bathed in socialism“ on the Adriatic coast (*Grandits, H. and Taylor, K., 2010*), played a crucial role in both economic prosperity and the formation of Montenegro's destination identity.

When it comes to tourism in post-war Yugoslavia, Montenegro, despite being the smallest and least developed of the six republics of SFRY, had some distinct characteristics. Specifically, in terms of number of visitors and overnight stays, Montenegro had the highest share of tourist traffic in the former state, with per capita rates four times higher than the Yugoslav average (*Leković, S., 2002*).

The period of intense and dynamic tourism development in Montenegro began in 1960 with the opening of one of the world's most exclusive hotels, which was awarded the prestigious Golden Apple in 1972 by the International Organization of Tourism Journalists and Writers. The initiative to transform the former fishing village of St. Stefan into a luxury city-hotel originated from the highest political echelons of former Yugoslavia. Furthermore, for its achievements in tourism, the Montenegrin tourist metropolis Budva was named the tourism champion of the former Yugoslavia in 1987, a year marked by exceptional success according to all relevant indicators (*Jovanović, I. and Vitić-Četković, A., 2012*).

Thus, the period of socialism in Montenegro also represents a period of touristification, which involves the transformation of spatial, socio-economic, and cultural characteristics of receptive regions under the influence of tourism (*Vojnović, N., 2016*). On the other hand, this period also signifies as a historical steppingstone towards the national emancipation and the establishment of the sovereign state of Montenegro, where tourism represents a dominant economic sector.

THE BEGINNINGS OF TOURISM VALORISATION OF SOCIALIST CULTURAL HERITAGE IN POST-YUGOSLAV MONTENEGRO

Despite the promotion of the cliché of brotherhood and unity among the peoples and nationalities, after the conflicts during the 1990s, Yugoslavia disintegrated into six independent states amid great human tragedies. This was followed by a general wave of discontent towards Tito's legacy and the socialist, as well as the anti-fascist, legacy. Almost all the main streets in Yugoslav cities named after Josip Broz Tito were renamed. This development also affected Montenegro, although it had distinguished itself in the National Liberation War by organizing the first anti-fascist uprising in Europe (July 13th, 1941, in Virpazar) and having the highest percentage of national heroes in the National Liberation War relative to the population. The capital of Montenegro, Titograd, was renamed Podgorica in 1992.

During the period of the restoration of Montenegrin statehood in 2006, emphasis was placed on the Petrović-Njegoš dynasty, specifically the period of recognition (Berlin Congress 1878) and the development of Montenegro as a sovereign state. However, after only two decades, in the time of the global economic crisis when a new wave of nationalism and fear of terrorism is sweeping through Europe, the phenomenon of "Yugonostalgia" and "Titostalgia" (*Velikonja, M. 2008*) is growing stronger in Montenegro, as well as in the former Yugoslavia. Although Montenegro was the poorest of all the Yugoslav republics during Tito's era and has been a candidate for EU membership since 2010, there is a growing appreciation for the socialist achievements of Yugoslavia in the region. These achievements included negligible unemployment, guaranteed pensions, free education and healthcare, low crime rates, and so on. This is supported by the words: "Although the violent breakup of socialist Yugoslavia continues to cast a shadow on people's memories of the former country, some 'sunnier' aspects of daily life during socialism seem to resist historical amnesia" (*Grandits, H. and Taylor, K, 2010*).

Post-socialist and post-Yugoslav Montenegro is emerging as a growing destination brand on the global tourism market. Furthermore, Montenegro's economy is highly dependent on tourism, contributing 25.5% to its GDP in 2023 (*Monstat, 2024*). This country, with a population of just 620,000, boasts a unity of diversity within a very small territory and a rich multicultural historical heritage from various eras. This has led tourism to become the main development strategy chosen by the country after regaining independence.

Recently, initiatives have emerged to touristically valorise the cultural heritage of the former SFRY in Montenegro. Among the former Yugoslav republics, Montenegro is unique in having a registered NGO named the *General Consulate of SFRY*, which is considered a tourist attraction in the city. Among the activities of this consulate, located in the coastal municipality of Tivat (known for the former naval shipyard Arsenal, now Porto Montenegro, one of the largest superyacht marinas in the Mediterranean), is the active celebration of the most significant holidays of the former SFRY. Furthermore, in 2015, Tito's luxury Blue Train (built in 1959) was promoted as a hotel on wheels, with a journey organized from Belgrade to Montenegro for 120 Western European tourists on one of Europe's most attractive railway lines, a construction project from Tito's era. Additionally, a Yugonostalgic tour for VIP guests from France was organized for Tito's birthday on May 25th. Moreover, Tito's villa in Igalo, one of his many residences in the former

Yugoslavia, can now be visited by tourists with a guide. Additionally, on November 29th, the Day of the former SFRY was commemorated at Montenegro's most luxurious hotel, *Regent-Porto Montenegro*. Montenegrin designer Slobodanka Seka Martinović presented a multimedia project and fashion show dedicated to Marshal Tito's wife, titled "Comrade Broz – A Tribute to a Woman and an Era,"¹¹ in Podgorica and other cities in 2015. What is more, there are initiatives for the revitalization of National Liberation War monuments and the establishment of an art gallery from the non-aligned era in Podgorica, as well as the opening of a National Liberation War museum in Cetinje, among other efforts.

Therefore, Socialism, is returning as a brand (*Duda, D, 2010*) through the valorization of socialist cultural heritage – cleansed of conflict and interpretative disputes, and presented as a finished product, now accessible to everyone.

TITO AND TITOGRAĐ AS RETRO-NARRATIVES OF PODGORICA DESTINATION

Podgorica, as the capital city with numerous natural and anthropogenic tourist values, is still more a business and transit centre within the corridor of tourism flows along the Adriatic coast and the northern, mountainous part of Montenegro, has yet to establish a clearly differentiated destination image. This Mediterranean climate city, with its river and lake resources, mountain ranges, plains, vineyards, national and regional parks, and numerous cultural and historical monuments, lacks a distinct tourist identity. Archaeological sites such as the Roman-era Duklja Park, the Illyrian site of Medun, and the Ottoman-era Clock Tower, Old town are recognized in Podgorica's destination image as places of cultural and civilizational convergence.

On the other hand, the period of Tito's rule, or the socialist landscape of the former Titograd, is both marginalised and unintegrated into Podgorica's destination image.

¹¹ <https://www.vijesti.me/zabava/zanimljivo/164048/drugarica-broz-omaz-zeni-i-jednom-vremenu>

Image 2: A Postcard from Titograd¹²

This does not correspond to the fact that Montenegro, like the other former Yugoslav republics, developed and maintained the cult of personality around Marshal Tito. Namely, every Republic and province in SFRY had a city with Tito's name. These were the cities of Titov Drvar (Bosnia and Herzegovina), Titova Korenica (Croatia), Titova Mitrovica (Kosovo), Titovo Užice (Serbia), Titov Velež (Macedonia), Titovo Velenje (Slovenia) and Titov Vrbas (Vojvodina), while Montenegro was the only one to name the city Titograd and not Tito's Podgorica.

On July 13th, 1946, Podgorica was renamed Titograd. The city retained this name for almost half a century, until April 2nd, 1992, when it was renamed Podgorica again through a referendum. One reason is that, from today's perspective, the period of Josip Broz Tito's rule is associated with a totalitarian social order in which human rights were violated and political freedoms were absent. The lack of political pluralism, suppression of dissenting opinions, the existence of the title of lifelong President of Yugoslavia, and the cultivation of a personality cult with mass celebrations of Tito's birthday, among other characteristics, point to the presence of political uniformity. However, the profile of Yugoslav diplomacy during Tito's rule shows that Tito was a skilled statesman, and Yugoslavia was a much more prosperous country compared to many other in Eastern and Central European countries.

¹² <https://www.portalanalitika.me/clanak/240393--zivjeti-i-umrijeti-u-titogradu>

Citizens who remember Tito's era recall primarily the economic and social stability¹³, worker self-management as the backbone of society, free healthcare and education, and the culture of brotherhood and unity.¹⁴

Image 3: Tito in Podgorica, 1959¹⁵

The long-serving president of the SFRY visited the capital of Montenegro 15 times.¹⁶ He left a deep impact on its history, as well as on the history of Montenegro. Despite the renaming of streets across the former Yugoslavia, one boulevard in Podgorica still bears the name of Josip Broz, the prominent global statesman who was respected by leaders of all three of the then-existing blocs – Eastern, Western, and Non-Aligned.

In 2019, at the proposal of the Assembly of the Capital City, a monument to the lifelong president of the SFRY was erected in Podgorica on St. Petar Cetinjski Boulevard. Opponents of this decision highlighted Tito's role in Montenegro's totalitarian legacy during his long rule, while supporters argued that the monument to Tito symbolizes freedom and anti-fascist orientation, and at the same time it honours a revolutionary and advocate for understanding and cooperation among peoples worldwide¹⁷.

¹³ https://www.slobodnaevropa.org/a/tito_godisnjica_crna_gora/2032380.html

¹⁴ <https://arhiva.tacno.net/naslovnica/izmedu-nostalgije-i-kulture-sjecanja-sve-nase-traume-nakon-raspada-jugoslavije/>

¹⁵ <https://sharemontenegro.me/vremeplov-tito-u-crnoj-gori-septembra-1959/>

¹⁶ <https://www.slobodnaevropa.org/a/tito-titograd-spomenik/29573365.html>

¹⁷ <https://www.slobodnaevropa.org/a/tito-titograd-spomenik/29573365.html>

Image 4: Tito's monument erected in Podgorica in 2019.¹⁸

New ideological frameworks in post-socialist Montenegro have led to the monument being targeted by vandals and exposed to graffiti and defacement. Nevertheless, Tito as a retro-narrative continues to be perceived between myth and reality.

SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the purposes of this paper, a survey was conducted focusing on the potential for reviving the material and immaterial cultural heritage of the former Titograd from a tourism perspective. A total of 105 questionnaires were completed.

Approximately 55.2% of the survey participants (58 respondents) indicated that retro motifs, or elements of the socialist cultural heritage of the former Titograd, should be further integrated into Podgorica's destination brand. Meanwhile, 25.7% (27 respondents) felt that they should not, and 19.1% (20 respondents) were undecided.

According to 48.6% of the survey participants (51 respondents) the main motivation for visitors and tourists to explore the socialist cultural heritage of Titograd would be to learn more about the advantages and disadvantages of life under socialism. Meanwhile, 30.5% (32 respondents) would be motivated by the opportunity to briefly experience life in Tito's Yugoslavia, and 20.1% (22 respondents) would be interested in connecting with their ancestors.

¹⁸ Photo: Adel Omeragic - Anadolu Agency

43.8% of the survey participants (46 respondents) consider monuments from the socialist period to be acceptable or particularly suitable for tourist valorisation, while 27.6% (29 respondents) view them as events from the socialist era. Meanwhile, 19% (20 respondents) find the way of life during the socialist period to be suitable for tourist valorization.

Among the various proposed solutions for the tourist valorization of the socialist cultural heritage of Titograd, 58.1% of the survey participants (61 respondents) chose the establishment of a themed museum. According to 67.6% (71 respondents), organizing exhibitions on the theme of Titograd's socialist cultural heritage is necessary, while 62.9% (66 respondents) support the idea of creating an open-air themed museum. Creating a digitized thematic trail focused on Titograd's socialist cultural heritage is considered an acceptable solution by 78.1% (82 respondents), and 85.7% (90 respondents) advocate for the opening of tourist and hospitality facilities in a "Yugo-retro" style.

Tourist offer creators in Podgorica recognize the potential for valorizing the socialist cultural heritage of Titograd according to 3.8% of the survey participants (4 respondents), while 92.4% (97 respondents) believe it is not recognized, and 3.8% of the survey participants (4 respondents) are undecided on this issue. According to 11.4% of the survey participants (12 respondents), tourist products themed around the socialist period, which fall under the category of dark tourism, should be created in Podgorica. However, 82% (86 respondents) believe that tourist products themed around the socialist period of dark tourism should not be created, as has been done in countries like Romania and Poland. 7.6% (8 respondents) were undecided on this matter.

About 57.1% of the survey participants (60 respondents) believe that "Tito-tourism" can be an effective form of valorizing Yugonostalgia in Podgorica, while 22.9% (24 respondents) consider this view to be inaccurate or unacceptable. On the other hand, 20% (21 respondents) were undecided on this issue. In terms of the effective role in the tourism valorization of the intangible and material socialist cultural heritage of Titograd, 24.8% of the survey participants (26 respondents) think that state institutions (Government, Ministries) should play a greater role, 36.2% (38 respondents) believe local government should have a more effective role, 17.1% (18 respondents) think the National Tourism Organization (NTO) should take a bigger role, and 29.5% (31 respondents) believe the Local Tourism Organization should be more involved. Under "other" (19% or 2 respondents), suggestions included "communists" and "local communities of Podgorica".

In summing up, the research results indicate a range of possibilities for creating value, specifically for the tourism valorization of Titograd and the “Tito” narrative from the perspective of retro-marketing and nostalgic tourism. In this regard, we provide the following recommendations for destination managers in Podgorica:

- Opening a theme park, or a designated area featuring former socialist monuments.
- Creating a digitized thematic trail "Smart Titograd" through which tourists and visitors can learn about life in Tito's Yugoslavia, including aspects like leisure activities, consumer culture, standard of living, citizen participation in social self-management, and anecdotes from socialist everyday life.
- Encouraging entrepreneurial initiatives such as opening a themed hotel-museum and hospitality services in a "Yugo-retro" style.
- Reviving the spirit of solidarity from youth actions and brigades that could, under modern conditions, represent activities related to voluntourism¹⁹. Some of these activities could include marking mountain trails, reforestation of the destination, and environmental clean-up efforts.
- Organizing interactive performances and events such as meetings of nostalgic groups “Once Upon a Time in Titograd,” gatherings of pioneers, comrades, and friends, etc.
- Promoting events such as “Graffiti and Street Art of Titograd.”
- Valorising Yugonostalgia through “Tito-tourism” by creating guided tours such as “Tito and Titograd as a Cultural Landscape.”

CONCLUSION

In post-socialist Europe, both material and immaterial socialist cultural heritage are increasingly commodified, but they also enable the strengthening of local community identities as a response to tourists' search for authentic destination experiences. This is because the transmission of cultural and historical experiences forms a crucial part of tourist travel and destination experiences. Accordingly, there is consideration of the possibilities for the tourism valorization

¹⁹ "Voluntourism is a combination of volunteering and tourism, used to describe tourist trips taken with the intention to volunteer for an organisation in a foreign (usually less developed) country." (Magrivos, S., Kostopoulos, I. and Powers, L. 2021)

of socialist cultural heritage in Montenegro and Podgorica, the capital city with an insufficiently defined destination image.

Although the period of Marshal Tito's rule, from today's perspective, is viewed as a time of repression, the imminent war and harsh transition period following his death contributed to the emergence of Yugonostalgia in the countries of the former SFRY. Yugonostalgia can also be seen as an escape to another time unburdened by current geopolitical and socio-economic relations, but also an expression of protest due to social turmoil and insecurity and nationalist wave. The research conducted for this paper indicates that instead of relinquishing, there should be a marketing focus on tourist attractions related to the “Yugoretro” style and the socialist landscape of the former Titograd. Additionally, it is important to revive the spirit of solidarity and community as fundamental social values also within the framework of contemporary voluntourism. The *non-dark tourism* approach in this study has shown that the Tito narrative can be symbolically valued in terms of Montenegro's commitment to anti-fascist orientation, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of recent Montenegrin history.

The tourist experience of a destination is also based on the preservation of collective memory by the local community and on historical time travel. Through retro-marketing approach, thematic development, and digital (smart) solutions, socialist cultural heritage as a memorial value cannot only be integrated into Podgorica's destination image, but also it can contribute to the city's development as diversified and sustainable tourism destination.

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